

The 7th Biennial International Conference of OWSD Nigeria National Chapter

**ORGANIZATION FOR WOMEN IN SCIENCE FOR THE DEVELOPING WORLD (OWSD)
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE (FUTA)
BRANCH**

Email: owsd@futa.edu.ng

Tel: 08164584482, 08060097865

TOPIC: FOSTERING A SMARTER SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGY ECOSYSTEM

Chief Host

Professor Adenike Temidayo Oladiji, FAS
Vice Chancellor, FUTA

Convener

Professor Olayinka Ibiwumi Nwachukwu

Chair, LOC

Professor Folasade Mayowa Olajuyigbe

OWSD Southwest Coordinator

Professor Oluwatoyin Adenike Olaseinde

OWSD FUTA Branch Coordinator

Dr. Mosunmola Lydia Adeleke

LOC Members

1. Prof. Folasade Olajuyigbe - Chairperson
2. Dr. Oritoke Okeowo – Secretary
3. Mrs. Tolulope Orungbemi – Assistant Secretary
4. Prof. Bolanle Ojokoh – Scientific
5. Prof. Folasade Dahunsi – Programme
6. Prof. Oluwayemisi Adeparusi – Advisory
7. Prof. Oluwatoyin Olaseinde – Finance
8. Prof. Oluwatoyin Agbonifo – Technical
9. Prof. Helen Ogunsuyi – Awards
10. Prof. Omowunmi Oyeleke – Welfare
11. Dr. Mosunmola Adeleke – Logistics
12. Prof. Oluwayomi Faromika – Publicity
13. Dr. Esther Oyebode – Exhibitions
14. Dr. Adejoke Kolawole – Communique and Evaluation

Editorial Note

This Conference Proceedings presents a collection of full research papers accepted for presentation at the 7th Biennial International Conference of the Organisation for Women in Science for the Developing World (OWSD) Nigeria National Chapter, held from 7–10 July 2025 at the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

The conference, themed “Fostering a Smarter Scientific and Technological Ecosystem,” featured peer-reviewed oral and poster presentations addressing both global and local scientific and technological challenges. The papers published in this volume span a wide range of interdisciplinary research areas, including agriculture and food security; climate and environmental sustainability; biotechnology and nanoscience; engineering and renewable energy; nutrition and health; medical innovations; artificial intelligence and digital technologies; open science and science education; and gender, diversity, and peacebuilding.

All submissions underwent a peer-review and editorial process in accordance with the conference’s academic standards prior to publication. The editorial team focused on improving structure, clarity, and consistency; however, the responsibility for the accuracy of data, analyses, interpretations, and conclusions rests solely with the authors. While every effort has been made to ensure quality, minor errors or omissions may remain.

These proceedings are published as an open-access resource on Zenodo, each paper being assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to ensure persistent access, visibility, and citability. The views expressed in the papers do not necessarily reflect those of the Organizing Committee or OWSD Nigeria National Chapter.

For post-publication corrections or inquiries, please contact ow sdfuta25@gmail.com or the Conference Secretariat.

— *The Editorial Team*

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Prof. Bolanle Ojokoh

Sub-Theme Editors

1. Prof. Helen Ayo-Omogie
2. Dr. Olukemi Adebola
3. Prof. Stephen Adeniyi Adefegha
4. Dr. Aderinola Joyce Awoniyi
5. Dr. Bosede Ojo
6. Dr. Ochuko Ojo
7. Dr. Oluchi Okere
8. Prof. Olutayo Boyinbode
9. Prof. Olufunmilayo Oladipo
10. Prof. Ebun-Oluwa Oladele

Review Process Managers

1. Dr. Abimbola Afolayan
2. Dr. Oluchi Okere
3. Dr. Oritoke Okeowo
4. Dr. Mary Kinga
5. Dr. Sadura Akinrinwa
6. Dr. Adebukola Adefisayo

Proceedings Secretariat Officer

1. Dr. Mary Kinga

Editorial Assistant

1. Mr. Bimbo Ayeyemi

Reviewers

1. Prof. M. Adegbenro
2. Prof. O.O. Awolu
3. Prof. R.A. Adebayo
4. Prof. (Mrs.) D. Adegunloye
5. Prof. (Mrs.). B.O.T. Ifesan
6. Prof. S.O. Oladeji
7. Dr. (Mrs.) A. Akintomide
8. Dr. A.J. Adeyemo
9. Dr. L.S. Fayeun
10. Dr. (Mrs.) A.O. Abidemi-Iromini
11. Dr. (Mrs.) T. Igejongbo
12. Dr. A.O. Ayeni
13. Dr. (Mrs.) O.V. Ayodele
14. Dr. (Mrs.) F.I. Wole-Alo
15. Dr. (Mrs.) O.R. Adegbanke
16. Dr. (Mrs.) A.I. Akinyede
17. Mr. O.S. Fasuhanmi
18. Dr. O. G. Adebola.
19. Dr. R. J. Kolawole.
20. Dr. D.F. Oke.
21. Dr. Adejoke Naomi Kolawole
22. Dr. Aderinola Joyce Awoniyi
23. Dr. Ayokunle Olubode Ademosun

24. Dr. Kikelomo Folake Jaiyesimi
25. Dr. Olusola Tosin Lawal
26. Dr. Oreoluwa Moyosore Daniel
27. Prof. Bukola Christiana Adedayo
28. Dr. Fatima Alaba Mohammed
29. Mrs. Omonigho Angela Israel
30. Dr. Okere Oluchi
31. Prof. E.G. Dada
32. Dr. E. B. Ajulo
33. Dr. Iyanu Adegun
34. Dr. A. H. Afolayan
35. Dr. I. A. Makinde
36. Dr. Oluwaseyi F. Afe
37. Dr. Asegunloluwa Babalola
38. Dr. O. A. Odeniyi
39. Dr. Bosede Ojo
40. Dr. A.A. Komolafe
41. Dr. G.M. Olayanju

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Smart Agriculture and Food Security (SAF) – Track 1

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdsaf/>

- Biological and Toxicological Effects of Aqueous Extract of *Strychnos Spinosa* (spiny monkey orange) Leaf on “*Heteroclaris*” (SAF 012) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172169>
- Biomass Allocation and Yield Potential of Sweet Potato Varieties under Rain-Fed Conditions (SAF 024) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172346>
- Chemical Profiling of *Bambusa Vulgaris* Leaf Essential Oils from Southwest Nigeria: Identification of Bioactive Compounds and Their Pharmacological Potential (SAF 016) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172422>
- Evaluation of Genetic Diversity of Local and Exotic Tomatoes using Morphological Traits and Simple Sequence Repeat Molecular Markers (SAF 039) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172536>
- Factors Influencing Smallholder Farmers’ Participation in Tomato Production in Ondo State, Nigeria (SAF 029) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172628>
- Fungal Pathogens Responsible for Diseases in Carrot (*Daucus Carota* L.) Production in Ondo State Nigeria (SAF 036) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172770>
- Nutrient and Anti-Nutrient Content of Wheat-Cassava Composite Flour (SAF 014) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172846>
- Performance and Egg Quality Parameters of Laying Hens Fed Diets Supplemented with Processed Bioash (SAF 011) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172944>
- Phenotypic Variability and Growth Performance of Three Nigerian Chickens Reared in South-East Nigeria (SAF 013) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18173039>
- Prevalence and Antimicrobial Resistance Profiling of *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* in Leafy Vegetables from Open Markets in Abakaliki, Nigeria: Implications for Food Safety and Public Health (SAF 033) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18173092>
- Tourism Entrepreneurship and Women Livelihood Assets in Beach Resorts, Lagos State Nigeria (SAF 044) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18173222>
- Effect of Varying Temperatures on the Properties of Honey From Different Sources (SAF 022) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18237980>

- Evaluation Of Proximate Composition, Lycopene Content, Betacarotene Content And DNA Quality Profiling In Tomato Varieties, *Lycopersicon Esculentum* (Mill.) (SAF 026) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18237866>
- Efficacy of *Fagara Zanthoxyloides* And *Andkigelia Africana* Extracts in Protecting Sugarcane Against Subterranean Termites (SAF 035) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18255413>

Climate Change, Earth Sciences and Environmental Sustainability (CEE) – Track 2

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdcee/>

- Assessment of Deforestation in Ife North Local Government Area, Osun State (CEE 011) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18170827>
- Assessment of Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Water at Selected Stations of Mokuro Lake, Ile-Ife, Nigeria (CEE 021) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18170943>
- Determination of Specific Absorption Rate from Mobile Phones on Active Call Within Sokoto Metropolis, Northwest, Nigeria (CEE 041) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171063>
- Dynamics and Hydrocarbon Degrading Potential of Microorganisms Associated with Long-Term Polluted Site in South-South Nigeria (CEE 003) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171231>
- Integrating Sustainable Design in Southwest Nigerian University Buildings to Mitigate Climate Change Impacts on Staff and Students (CEE 010) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171380>

Engineering, Renewable Energy and Blue Economy (ERB) – Track 4

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsderb/>

- Assessment of *Bacillus Cereus* Isolated from Petrochemical Waste (Bitumen) for Electricity Generation Using Microbial Fuel Cell Technology (ERB 002) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171585>
- Carbon Dioxide Capturing using Activated Carbon Produced from Orange Peels (ERB 010) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171716>

- Evaluation of the Fuel Value Indices of Selected Wood Fuel Species Used in Nigeria (ERB 013) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171820>
- Investigation of the Potential Use of Termite Mound Soil in Brick Production (ERB 005) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171906>
- Location–Allocation of Waste Bins in the University of Ibadan (ERB 004) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171999>

Sustainable Nutrition, Phytomedicine, Nutraceuticals and Human Health (SPN) – Track 5

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owdsdpn/>

- Acaricidal Effect of Spondias Mombin Leaf Extract on Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) Microplus Female Tick (SPN 086) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163626>
- Antibacterial Effects of Yoghurt on Selected Diarrhoeagenic Bacteria (SPN 051) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163914>
- Antibiogram Profiles of Salmonella Typhi Isolated from Typhoid Fever Patients in Akure, Nigeria and Effects of Some Herbal Concoctions on Antibiotic Resistant Strains (SPN 042) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164180>
- Characterization of Bacillus Species from Fresh Fruits and Their Biodegradation Potential in the Reduction of Heavy Metal Contents in Banana Juices (SPN 082) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164296>
- Microbial Assessment of Some Selected Ready-to-Eat Food Samples in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria (SPN 077) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164436>
- Molecular Interaction and Antidiabetic Potential of Indian Heliotrope (heliotropium indicum) Leaf Extract: Inhibition of Human Salivary α -amylase and Antioxidant Profiling" (SPN 074) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164644>
- Neuroprotective Effect of Centella Asiatica Leaf Alkaloid Extract on Enzymes Linked with Aluminium-Induced Alzheimer's Disease in Drosophila Melanogaster (SPN 044) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18165880>
- Nutrients Enhancement and Organoleptic Properties of Cheese-Like Products from Cashew Nuts (Anacardium Occidentale) Spiced with Alligator Pepper, Garlic and Ginger (SPN 015) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168008>

- Nutritional and Health Benefits of Black Plum (*Syzygium Cumini*) for Human Well-Being (SPN 084) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168105>
- Phytochemical Characterization and Inhibitory Mechanism of African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum Albidum*) Ethanolic Seed Extract on Human Salivary A-Amylase (SPN 078) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168197>
- Phytochemical Screening and Inhibitory Activities of A-Glucosidase and A-Amylase of Aqueous Extract of *Amaranthus Hybridus* Leaves (SPN 075) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168289>
- The Evaluation of the Solvent Fractions of the Fruits, Leaves, and the Stem Bark of *Sarcocephalus Latifolius* (sm.) E. A. Bruce for Cytotoxicity and Antioxidant Activities (SPN 018) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168364>
- Toxicity Studies on Sorghum Bicolor Infusion Mixed with Different Additives on Selected Organs in Weanling Rats (SPN 039) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168405>
- Understanding Typhoid Fever Transmission Dynamics in The Presence of Multiple Interventions– Optimal Control and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (SPN 045) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18168472>

Precision Medicine and Healthcare Innovations (PMH) - Track 6

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdpmh/>

- A Systematic Review on Obesity and Aging: The Two-Stringed Precursors for Osteoarthritis (PMH 024) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18255527>
- COVID-19 in Immunocompromised Hosts: A Systematic Review of Disease Severity, Immune Response, and Clinical Management Strategies (PMH 030) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18255656>
- Suppression of Hepatic Inflammation by Camel Milk in Rats Exposed to Monosodium Glutamate (PMH 007) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18262230>

Artificial Intelligence, Security and Digital Technologies (ASD) – Track 7

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdasd/>

- Design of an Intelligent Covid-19 Spread Analytics and Policy Support System (ASD 018) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152920>
- Development of a Secure Web-Based Logbook System for the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (ASD 002) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18116608>
- Development of a Web-Based Rainfall Forecasting System Using Long Short-Term Memory Networks (ASD 003) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18153959>
- Distribution and Analysis of Negative Headlines in Nigerian News: A Scalable Computational Framework (ASD 019) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18153290>
- Predicting Students' Learning Styles in an Educational Digital Game System Using Support Vector Machines (ASD 011) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18132136>
- Prediction of University Network Traffic Behaviour using LSTM and OGRU (ASD 034) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18153668>
- Spoken Command Recognition System for Hands-Free Door Control (ASD 027) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18153571>
- User Acceptance and Usability Insights from A Pilot Study of an Integrated Wearable and Contact Tracing App in Nigeria (ASD 017) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152477>
- Watermarking Biometric System for Human Ownership Identification (ASD 013) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18134383>

Open Science Initiatives, and Trends in Science and Technical Education (OTT) - Track 8

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdott/>

- Role of Mathematics and Computer Science Education in Strengthening Early Childhood STEM Learning: A Prerequisite for Innovative National Growth and Development (OTT 004) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18234663>

Gender Issues, Diversity and Conflict Resolution (GDC) – Track 9

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owsdgdc/>

- Analysis of Time-Use Pattern Among Rural and Urban Women in Ondo State, Nigeria (GDC 005) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163210>

- Combating Online Gender-Based Violence: A Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Framework for Evaluating Information Security Solutions (GDC 013) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163366>
- The Participation Paradox: Why Female Farmers Sell More but Earn Less in Nigeria's Staple Crop Markets (GDC 007) - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163510>